

Phytochemical Investigation of *Vateria indica*

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VATERIA indica (Fam.: Dipterocarpaceae) occurs in the evergreen forests of the Western Ghats from North Kanara to Kerala in India. The resin (white Dammar) of the tree and Dhupa fat of the seeds are commercially important and have medicinal¹ uses also. The bark² and seeds³ have already been examined for their chemical constituents.

The present communication reports the chemical constituents of the leaves and roots collected from Karnataka state (India). The column chromatography of the combined acetone and alcohol extract of the leaves over silica gel gave two pure compounds A and B. The same compounds were isolated from the roots. Compound A (1%) was crystallised from aqueous ethanol as rectangular prisms, m.p. 154–56°. It was identified as bergenin⁴ a C-glucoside by uv, nmr and superimposable ir spectra. Compound B (0.42%) was crystallised from chloroform–methanol as white solid, m.p. > 350°; $[\alpha]_D^{25} -400^\circ$ (MeOH). The uv, ir, nmr, mass spectra and C and H analyses were comparable with those reported for hopeaphenol⁴; B being identified as hopeaphenol.

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The ¹³C nmr spectra of hopeaphenol (not reported earlier) in DMSO-d₆ showed the following resonances. Three aliphatic doublets for six non-oxygenated carbons (one signal swamped by DMSO, 47.17, 48.40 ppm), one aliphatic doublet at 86.83

ppm for two aliphatic oxygenated carbons, eight aromatic doublets for 24 aromatic carbons (94.13 to 129.04), six quaternary carbon singlets (116.81 to 140.59) for twelve carbon atoms and six phenolic singlets (154.58 to 157.86) for 12 carbons (the designation singlet and doublet refer to the appearance of the resonance in the single frequency off resonance mode experiments). Probable assignment based on substituent parameters⁵ are shown in structure of hopeaphenol (1).

This is the first report of the occurrence of bergenin and hopeaphenol in the leaves and roots. The leaves can be used as a source of bergenin as it occurs in 1% yield. Hopeaphenol was found fungicidal against two wood rotting fungi, namely, *Poria monticola* (at 0.05 and 0.1% level) and *Polyporus versicolor* (at 0.1% level).

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Surface Hydrocarbons from the Leaves of some *Cassia* Species

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It is a well known fact that surface lipids have a vital role in conducting transpiration and leaf surface properties. Moreover, the composition of lipids and particularly hydrocarbon distribution, has also been suggested as a parameter in chemotaxonomy¹⁻⁴. But this approach has not always met with unambiguous success⁵⁻⁷ since wax composition may vary not only with the environmental history but also with the age of the

plant^{5,6,8}. The present communication is related to the analyses of surface hydrocarbons present in the leaves of four *Cassia* species, viz. *C. siamea* Lam., *C. sophora* Linn., *C. fistula* Linn. and *C. occidentalis* Linn. This is a part of our programme towards investigating the distribution of surface hydrocarbons as well as the composition of surface lipids of leaves in different species of the family Leguminosae.

The surface wax was extracted in cold n-hexane (analytical grade) in the usual way from the fresh leaves of the above species, collected from the Burdwan University campus and then the solvent was removed under reduced pressure. In each case, the crude extract was fractionated through preparative tlc using CCl₄ as a chromatographic solvent. The hydrocarbon band was identified through co-tlc studies with standard paraffins. The eluted band showed no carbonyl absorption in the infrared region and the absence of alkene was confirmed through argentometric tlc⁹. The purified hydrocarbon fraction was analysed directly by a programmed glc run (oven temp., 170–300° at 5° min⁻¹; initial period 1 min and final period 15 min) on a 10% SE-30 glass column (2 m × 1/8" i.d.) with flame ionisation detector and N₂ as a carrier gas in a Becker gas chromatograph (Packard 419) and characterised through co-glc run with authentic samples of n-alkanes (Sigma). The analyses of hydrocarbons present in the surface wax of leaves of four *Cassia* species are presented in Table 1. The analyses confirmed the presence

of all the members of n-alkane in the series C₁₆–C₃₅ in the cuticular waxes of the leaves of all the four species of *Cassia*. It appears that the distribution pattern of n-alkanes presented in Table 1 in the surface wax from the leaves of four *Cassia* species is very much in conformity with that expected for higher plants (namely, the most common occurrence of odd numbered n-alkanes in the range C₂₇–C₃₅). The predominant occurrence of lower even-numbered alkanes, like C₁₆, C₁₈, C₂₀ and some higher odd-numbered alkanes, like C₂₇, C₂₉, C₃₁, C₃₃ in all the species and also the presence of some higher even-numbered alkane, viz. C₂₈ and C₃₀ in *C. siamea* and *C. occidentalis* and C₃₂ in *C. fistula* and *C. occidentalis* in greater proportions were observed. It is interesting to note that the exhibited n-alkane distribution pattern of leaves of the four *Cassia* species are not similar (mainly differing in the distribution of C₁₆, C₂₈, C₂₉, C₃₀ and C₃₃ alkanes) although the composition ratio of odd-numbers to total alkanes of the described species differs a little. Therefore, it is now evident that such variation in the distribution pattern of leaf hydrocarbons of the four species in a single genus at the same environmental condition and at the same time (December, flowering stage of the plant) indicates that it may not be used as a taxonomic marker.

The occurrence of branched hydrocarbons as minor components in all *Cassia* species presented in the Table 1 is a characteristic feature for higher plants¹⁰.

TABLE 1—DISTRIBUTION OF HYDROCARBON CONSTITUENTS* OF THE LEAF WAX OF *Cassia* SPECIES

Carbon no. of n-alkanes	<i>Cassia siamea</i>	<i>Cassia sophora</i>	<i>Cassia fistula</i>	<i>Cassia occidentalis</i>
16	11.84	14.86	7.71	7.36
17	1.04	1.19	1.85	1.64
18	8.20	8.84	8.30	8.41
19	0.20	0.32	0.40	0.29
20	4.02	2.92	6.06	6.03
21	0.16	0.24	0.05	0.13
22	1.25	1.20	1.83	1.86
23	0.14	0.53	0.11	0.14
24	0.55	0.51	0.64	0.66
25	0.50	2.14	0.69	0.52
26	1.38	1.50	0.46	0.77
27	12.71	10.02	10.05	10.11
28	5.90	1.95	1.47	3.34
29	19.31	17.08	11.25	13.68
30	4.10	1.63	2.40	3.72
31	19.64	21.65	19.82	19.15
32	2.32	1.35	3.85	3.82
33	3.18	7.12	15.63	13.23
34	0.22	0.46	0.55	0.40
35	0.13	1.10	1.38	0.41
Branched chain alkanes	3.21	3.39	5.50	4.33
Composition ratio of odd members to total alkanes	58.91	63.54	64.80	62.00

*Values in mol %.

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